

Variation in dissolution behavior among different nanoforms and its implication for grouping approaches in inhalation toxicity

Johannes G. Keller^a, Michael Persson^b, Philipp Müller^a, Lan Ma-Hock^a, Kai Werle^a, Josje Arts^b, Robert Landsiedel^a, Wendel Wohlleben^{a,*}

^a BASF SE, Dept. Experimental Toxicology and Ecology, Dept. Material Physics, 67056 Ludwigshafen, Germany

^b Nouryon Pulp and Performance Chemicals AB, S-445 80 Bohus, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Dissolution
Transformation
Grouping
Lysosomal conditions
Extracellular conditions

ABSTRACT

Different nanoforms (NF) of the same substance each need to be registered under REACH, but similarities in physiological interaction -among them biodissolution- can justify read-across within a group of NFs, thereby reducing the need to perform animal studies. Here we focused on the endpoint of inhalation toxicity and explored how differences in physical parameters of 17 NFs of silica, and organic and inorganic pigments impact dissolution rates, half-times, and transformation under both pH 7.4 lung lining conditions and pH 4.5 lysosomal conditions. We benchmarked our observations against well-known TiO₂, BaSO₄ and ZnO nanomaterials, representing very slow, partial and quick dissolution respectively. By automated image evaluation, structural transformations were observed for dissolution rates in the order of 0.1 to 10 ng/cm²/h, but did not provide additional decision criteria on the similarity of NFs. Dissolution half-times spanned nearly five orders of magnitude, mostly dictated by the substance and simulant fluid, but modulated up to ten-fold by the subtle differences between NFs. Physiological time scales and benchmark materials help to frame the biologically relevant range, proposed as 1 h to 1 y. NFs of ZnO, Ag, SiO₂, BaSO₄ were in this range. We proposed numerical rules of pairwise similarity within a group, of which the worst case NF would be further assessed by in vivo inhalation studies. These rules divided the colloidal silica NFs into two separate candidate groups, one with Al-doping, one without. Shape or silane surface treatment were less important. The dissolution halftimes of many organic and inorganic pigment NFs were longer than the biologically relevant range, such that dissolution behavior is not an obstacle for their groupings.

1. Introduction

The performance of fillers and pigments depends not only on their chemical substance and purity, but also on the physical structure of the particles. For instance, pigment grades intended to give an opaque coating need particles sizes around 200 nm to optimize the scattering of light, whereas another grade of the same substance could be offered with particle sizes around 30 nm to obtain a transparent coating (Herbst and Hunger, 2006; Pfaff, 2017). Also the shape can contribute to the coloristic performance. Silica is another example of a substance with many different nanomaterial grades (Iler, 1979); specifically, colloidal silica used to reduce the consumption of energy in paper-making, is offered in spheroidal or elongated grades, which may have Aluminum surface

dopings to optimize the colloidal interaction between silica, starch and cellulose (Norell et al., 1999). Pigments and fillers are the nanomaterials of highest production volume on the European market (Ministère de l'Environnement, de l'Energie et de la Mer, 2015; Wigger et al., 2018). In general, grades that are optimized for specific purposes are specified by their crystallinity (or absence thereof), particle size, particle shape, specific surface area and surface treatment. Since January 2020, these same parameters define the different nanoforms of the substance (NF) that each need to be registered under the REACH regulation (Commission, E, 2018). REACH data requirements of the cumulated tonnage band apply to each of the NFs, such that for human hazard assessment the registrants have to perform OECD-guideline animal studies, specifically inhalation studies, for each NF. Alternatively, registrants use

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: johannes-georg.keller@basf.com (J.G. Keller), michael.persson@nouryon.com (M. Persson), philipp.mueller@basf.com (P. Müller), lan.ma-hock@basf.com (L. Ma-Hock), kai.werle@basf.com (K. Werle), josje.arts@nouryon.com (J. Arts), robert.landsiedel@basf.com (R. Landsiedel), wendel.wohlleben@basf.com (W. Wohlleben).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.impact.2021.100341>

Received 12 April 2021; Received in revised form 17 June 2021; Accepted 6 July 2021

Available online 12 July 2021

2452-0748/© 2021 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

concepts of grouping and read-across as suggested by the REACH legislation (Commission, E, 2018). The applicable ECHA guidance on grouping of NFs is setting the stage of the present contribution by stating “that differences in the physical parameters seen when characterising the (sets of) nanoforms does not per se exclude the possibility to apply read-across. Indeed, similarities in the parameters related to the behaviour (e.g. solubility) or those relating to their reactivity may be more important to consider when building a read-across justification.” (European_Chemical_Agency (ECHA), 2019) Here we provide such justification for NFs with well-characterised differences in physical parameters (size, shape, surface doping), for which we quantify the similarity in the dissolution and transformation that are fundamental to the behavior upon inhalation. In several grouping frameworks (Arts et al., 2015; Arts et al., 2014; Arts et al., 2016; Oomen et al., 2015) and methodical reviews (Steinhäuser and Sayre, 2017) the assessment of dissolution was prioritized. Some have argued the option of grouping based on transformations (Lamon et al., 2018; Lynch et al., 2014), as the lifecycle may actually increase the similarity of initially different nano-enabled products (NEPs) (Mitrano et al., 2015), e.g. by chemical re-speciation of metal-based NEPs (Conway et al., 2015; Pantano et al., 2018).

Inhaled NFs first get into contact with lung lining fluid (pH 7.4) and may then be phagocytosed by alveolar macrophages, where they are exposed to acidic phagolysosomal fluid (pH 4.5) (Oberdörster and Kuhlbusch, 2018). Either one can induce dissolution and transformation to a different extent for different substances, possibly further modulated by NF differences of size, shape and surface treatments (Avramescu et al., 2020; Fuentes et al., 2020; Gray et al., 2020; Gualtieri et al., 2019;

Koltermann-Jüilly et al., 2018; Koltermann-Jüilly et al., 2019). It has been proposed to prioritize dissolution testing in a medium that is most likely to react with the NF, or to dissolve it by non-redox (hydrolytic, acid-base) mechanisms (Gray et al., 2018), or even to perform sophisticated sequential incubations to mimic the passage through several compartments (Cai et al., 2020). Numerous simulant fluids have been employed (Kastury et al., 2017; Yokel et al., 2019), but standardisation has been initiated (Gao and Lowry, 2018; ISO/TR19057, 2017; Klaessig, 2018), and is ongoing in the current OECD WPMN guideline project 1.5 (Gray et al., 2020; Gray et al., 2018). The robustness of results from different laboratories is supported by benchmark materials from the repository of the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC) such as TiO₂ and ZnO, representing very slow and quick dissolution respectively (Keller et al., 2020c; Koltermann-Jüilly et al., 2019), and BaSO₄, representing partial dissolution with in vivo transformations (Keller et al., 2020). The assessment of the phenomenon of chemical and physical transformation of the remaining particles is far less standardised, but the NanoDefine project (Mech et al., 2020a; Mech et al., 2020b) has developed automated evaluation of TEM images into 16 structural descriptors that may help to reproducibly assess changes before and after dissolution testing (Verleyesen et al., 2019; Wagner, 2016).

Here we demonstrated how differences in physical parameters of several NFs of pigments and several NFs of silica from different production routes impact the dissolution rates, half-times, and transformation under simulated pulmonary conditions. We employ methods in line with the ongoing OECD guideline project: We assess dissolution

Fig. 1. Inhalation and pulmonary dissolution scheme. Particles reaching the deeper lung interact with lung lining fluid, simulated by Lung Simulant Fluid (LSF) pH 7.4, with the Gamble's composition of (Marques et al., 2011), which is a compilation recommended by (ISO/TR19057, 2017). Particles reaching alveoli are phagocytosed by macrophages and end up in lysosomes, which are then acidified to activate degradation, simulated by Phagolysosomal Simulant Fluid (PSF) pH 4.5, as recommended by (ISO/TR19057, 2017). The dissolution kinetics are assessed by a flow-through dynamic setup with previously validated fluid flow rates (Keller et al., 2020c; Koltermann-Jüilly et al., 2018); eluted ions are quantified by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICPMS), and eluted organics are quantified by calibrated UVVis spectrometry. Kinetics are evaluated by two interrelated descriptors: dissolution rate and dissolution half-time. The remaining solids, which are potentially transformed ENM, are investigated through Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) with automated (NanoDefine code) evaluation of 16 descriptors of size and shape.

and transformation in extracellular simulant (pH 7.4) and lysosomal simulant (pH 4.5) media (Fig. 1), and we explore the NanoDefine image evaluation to assess transformations. Our methodology and assessment shall support the implementation of the recent GRACIOUS framework for grouping and read-across of nanomaterials (Stone et al., 2020). For this purpose, numerical measures of the similarity between the dissolution behavior of NFs are required. Although methodical approaches of the present contribution may be useful as well for the justification of registering a set of similar NF (European_Chemicals_Agency_(ECHA), 2019), our main purpose here is to support read-across between NFs (or between sets) for the endpoint of lung toxicity, in line with the ECHA guidance (European_Chemical_Agency_(ECHA), 2019), thereby reducing the need to perform animal studies.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

To make this study representative for frequently used nanoparticles, a broad selection of relevant nanomaterials and nanofoms was used. This study includes 17 different nanomaterials. The tested materials differ in different aspects viz. chemical composition, size, crystallinity, shape as well as coating. Five of these materials were provided by JRC through the sponsorship program of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Ag NM300, BaSO₄ NM220, CeO₂ NM212, precipitated SiO₂ NM200, and ZnO NM110. The tested pigments including CuPhthalocyanine_nano (commercialised as Pigment Blue 15:1), CuPhthalocyanin_halogen (commercialised as Pigment Green 7), Fe₂O₃_nano_A and Fe₂O₃_nano_B, Diketopyrrolopyrrole pigments DPP_nano, DPP_non-nano and DPP_premixed were provided by BASF SE. Fe₂O₃_nano_A and Fe₂O₃_nano_B differ in size and shape (Table 1). The colloidal amorphous silica materials Silica_Al, Silica_anis_Al, Silica_Std, Silica_anis_Std and Silica_Silane were provided by Nouryon. The abbreviations indicate: “Al” an intentional surface modification by aluminum to optimize the efficacy as additive in paper-making; “silane” an organic surface modification by glycerol-propyl moieties from alkyl-tri-alkoxysilanes; “Std” the standard spheroidal shape; “anis” intentional elongated (anisotropic) shape. The production process for the various amorphous silica nanoparticles are shortly described as follows: from sand, raw glass is produced by fusing silica sand with soda (Na₂CO₃). The raw glass is then dissolved in water at elevated temperatures to make sodium silicate solution. The general principle to produce colloidal silica is to remove sodium from the sodium silicate via cationic ion exchange to form an acidic monomer containing solution. A 5 wt-% solution is fed into a stirred tank reactor where the condensation polymerization process starts and silica nanoparticles are formed. pH is increased with a NaOH or sodium silicate solution to increase the rate of polymerization and improve colloidal stability. After particle synthesis, the final product is concentrated to the desired level (15 to 50 wt-%) depending on the particle size. For the anisotropic silica nanoparticles (Silica_anis_Std, Silica_anis_Al) the colloidal stability is temporarily reduced during the synthesis to generate a controlled aggregation of the primary particles. For the surface modified products (Silica_Al, Silica_anis_Al, Silica_silane) the surface modification is applied in a final step before concentrating the products. Table 1 provides an overview of the tested materials and their properties, such as size, shape, surface area, and composition. Since the ECHA guidance refers to covalent surface treatments, Table 1 highlights two NFs that are physical mixtures with polymers that are intended to adsorb (non-covalently) to the surface and to increase colloidal stability. The weight loss in thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, given as mass-% in Table 1) is suitable to quantify organic components, and is often attributed to surface modification, although the weight loss may reach –100% in the case of purely organic NFs.

2.2. Methods

The dissolution setup was previously described by Koltermann-Jüly et al. (2018) and Keller et al. (2020) and is an adapted version of a dissolution setup for man-made vitreous fibers (MMVF) (De Meringo et al., 1994; Guldborg et al., 1995; Guldborg et al., 1998) adjusted to the small pore sizes required for nanomaterials. This adapted setup is in agreement with ISO19057:2017 and describes the dissolution rate as well as the half-time of ENM. Overall, the setup consists of three major components: the flow-through cell, the medium and the technique for quantification of the dissolved fraction. For each material, 1 mg was transferred onto a 5 kDa cellulose triacetate membrane (Sartorius Stedim Biotech GmbH, Goettingen, Germany) and inserted in the flow-through cell and topped by another 0.45 µm membrane. The cell as well as the compartment was filled with Phagolysosomal Simulant Fluid pH 4.5 (PSF) or Lung Simulant Fluid pH 7.4 (LSF) (composition in Tables S1 and S2). PSF was previously developed by NIOSH (Stefaniak et al., 2005) and is recommended to investigate the dissolution under lysosomal conditions by the ISO standard (ISO/TR19057, 2017). Based on an earlier comparison to in-vivo inhalation results (Koltermann-Jüly et al., 2018), we believe the acidic lysosomal condition to be best predictive of the biodissolution of inhaled NFs (of low aspect ratio), because they are effectively internalized by macrophages.

As complementary medium, we selected the well-known Gamble's medium that mimics the pH 7.4 condition of extracellular lung fluid; the ISO standard does not recommend a specific pH 7.4 medium but refers to (Marques et al., 2011), where we selected the original Gamble's medium (Table S2). For some metal-based NFs, this medium may exaggerate their potential to dissolve and transform, because it contains citrate to mimic the organic constituents (lipids, proteins) of the natural fluids (Table S2), which is a strong metal-ion chelator, and was discussed critically (Innes et al., 2021; Kastury et al., 2017). The dissolution half-time for SiO₂ and TiO₂ NFs may thus be underestimated because of the citrate content, but the structural transformation should be maximised for our methodical purpose to evaluate transformation as potential grouping criterion. We independently assessed that the dissolution rates of other metal-based NFs, specifically CeO₂, BaSO₄ and ZnO are far less sensitive to citrate (data not shown).

The filtration efficiency of the 5 kDa cellulose triacetate membrane was confirmed experimentally by measuring the particle size distribution, the mass concentration and number concentration before and after filtration (Fig. S3). The filtration efficiency was determined as >99.4%, limited by the quantification limit of the method. The size distribution after filtration (Fig. S4) is not indicative of a preferential size cut-off. This matches the expectation for a 5 kDa membrane, which nominally corresponds to a 1 to 2 nm cutoff, below the size range of all investigated materials (OECD, 2020). In contrast to alternatives such as dialysis bags (OECD, 2020), agglomeration and settling is no concern because the nanomaterials are held between two horizontal membranes, and constantly flushed by medium.

The flow cells were temperature-controlled in a water bath at 37 ± 0.5 °C. The flow rate was adjusted to 2 mL/h standard conditions. By comparison to well-characterised in-vivo inhalation clearance of TiO₂, ZnO and BaSO₄ nanomaterials, representing very slow, quick and partial dissolution respectively, we had previously calibrated the flow rate for best predictivity (Keller et al., 2020c).

Over a duration of 7 days, ten 10 mL eluate samples were analyzed for the ion concentration through either inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) (Nexion 2000b, Perkin Elmer Inc., Waltham, USA) for all inorganic materials or UV-vis spectrometry (Cary 60 UV-Vis Spectrometer, Agilent Technologies Inc., Santa Clara, USA). With ICP-MS all inorganic non-silicate materials had a limit of detection (LoD) of 0.1 µg/L with an external calibration of 0.1/1/10/100/1000 µg/L (ppb). For Ag, Ba and Ce the standard mode was used, whereas for Cu, Fe and Zn the kinetic energy discrimination (KED) with Helium gas was used (Hattendorf and Günther, 2004; Yamada, 2015). For the

Table 1
Overview of the properties of the 17 tested nanomaterials.

	CAS Number	Minimum external dimension (TEM or * AUC) [nm]	Shape (TEM) Descriptive	Specific Surface Area (BET) [m ² /g]	Surface modification	Surface composition (XPS) [%]	Weight loss, mean (associated organics) (TGA) [%]	Crystallinity/impurities (XRD) [%]
Ag NM300	7440-22-4	9	Spheroidal	N/A	noncovalently stabilised with polyvinylpyrrolidone	Ag: 1.9%, C: 66.5%, N: 3.2%, O: 28.5%	-17.9	Ag + amorphous (91.4%: 8.6%)
BaSO ₄ NM220	7727-43-7	32	Spheroidal	41	None	O 52%, Ba 13%, C 17%, S 11%, Cl 3%, P 3%, N 1%	-3.12	barium sulphate. Crystal structure: orthorhombic
CeO ₂ NM212	1306-38-3	40	Mixed spheroidal + platelets	27	None	C 79.9%, O 17.2%, Ce 2.4%	-0.97	Cerium oxide. Crystal structure: cubic (cerianite)
Cu_Phthalo_halogen	1328-53-5	14	Platelet	69	None	55.6% C; 0.8% O; 11.8% N; 1.4% metals; 30.3% non metals	-80.6	pigment green 7 + pigment green 36. Crystal structure: triclinic Degree of crystallinity = 72%
Cu_Phthalo_nano	147-14-8	17	Spheroidal	53	None	80.5% C; 9% O; 8.5% N; 1.4% metals; 0.7% non metals	-91.4	α-copperphthalocyanine. Crystal structure: triclinic Degree of crystallinity: 82%
DPP_nano	84,632-65-5	36	Spheroidal	94	None	77.1% C; 10.9% O; 5.9% N; 0% metals; 6.1% non metals	-98.3	3,6-bis(4-chlorophenyl)-2,5-dihydropyrrolo[3,4-c]pyrrole-1,4-dione]. Crystal structure: monoclinic Degree of crystallinity: 64%
DPP_non-nano	84,632-65-5	233	Spheroidal	16	None	79.4% C; 9.9% O; 5.1% N; 0.3% metals; 5.2% non metals	-93.9	3,6-bis(4-chlorophenyl)-2,5-dihydropyrrolo[3,4-c]pyrrole-1,4-dione]. Crystal structure: monoclinic Degree of crystallinity: 75%
DPP_premixed	84,632-65-5	400	Spheroidal	17	non-covalently premixed with polyacrylic acid	73.5% C; 9.5% O; 8.1% N; 0.4% metals; 8.6% non metals	-103	3,6-bis(4-chlorophenyl)-2,5-dihydropyrrolo[3,4-c]pyrrole-1,4-dione]. Crystal structure: monoclinic Degree of crystallinity: 74%
Fe ₂ O ₃ _nano_A	1309-37-1	15–130 × 4–21	Elongated	107	None	15.7% C; 54.2% O; 0% N; 28.2% metals; 1.9% non metals	-4	Iron(III) oxide. Crystal structure: Rombo.H.axes Degree of crystallinity: 95%
Fe ₂ O ₃ _nano_B	1309-37-1	37	Spheroidal	30	None	50.7% C; 33.7% O; 0% N; 15.6% metals; 0% non metals	-1.56	Iron(III) oxide. Crystal structure: Rombo.H.axes Degree of crystallinity: 95%
SiO ₂ NM200	7613-86-9	13	Spheroidal	190–220	None	O: 71.43%; Si: 20.30%; C: 5.96%; Na: 1.83%	-4.47	Silicium dioxide Structure: amorphous
Silica_Std	7631-86-9	10	Spheroidal	360 (Sears titration), 209 (TEM)	None	C: 16.9%, N: 7.7%, Na: 11.5%, O: 48.6%, Si: 15.2%	-1.56	Silicium dioxide Structure: amorphous
Silica_silane	7631-86-9	10	Spheroidal	216 (TEM)	Surface modified with glycerol-propyl moieties from alkyl-tri-alkoxysilanes	C: 10%, Na < 1%, O: 62.8%, Si: 26.3%	-2.72	Silicium dioxide Structure: amorphous
Silica_Al	7631-86-9	11	Spheroidal	360 (Sears titration), 175 (TEM)	Surface modification with Na-aluminate	Al: 1.1%, C: 6.1%, Na: 2.2%, O: 64.1%, Si: 26.4%	0	Silicium dioxide Structure: amorphous
Silica_anis_Std	7631-86-9	6	Elongated		None	Si: 28.6%, O: 65.4%,	0	Silicium dioxide Structure: amorphous

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

	CAS Number	Minimum external dimension (TEM or * AUC)	Shape (TEM)	Specific Surface Area (BET)	Surface modification	Surface composition (XPS)	Weight loss, mean (associated organics) (TGA)	Crystallinity/impurities (XRD)
		[nm]	Descriptive	[m ² /g]		[%]	[%]	[%]
Silica_anis_Al	7631-86-9	4	Elongated	800 (Sears titration),214 (TEM) 990 (Sears titration),427 (TEM)	Surface modification with Na-aluminate	C:3.7%, Na: 2.3%	0	Silicium dioxide Structure: amorphous
ZnO NM110	1314-13-2	42	mixed spheroidal and rods	12	None	Si: 24.9%, O: 63.4%, C:5.2%, Na: 3.8%, Al: 2.7% O: 38%; Zn: 35%; C: 30%; Cl: 3%; Na: 3%	-2.89	Zinc oxide ZnO >99%

silicate materials the LoD was 1 µg/L with an external calibration of 1/10/100/1000 µg/L (ppb) in KED mode. No digestion had to be performed since the eluted samples are inherently filtered, containing only dissolved species. Before the ICP-MS measurement, the instrument was tuned in accordance with the manufacturer's specification. The integration time was 50 ms and the argon flow of the Meinhardt nebulizer was 0.92 L/min. All samples were diluted by a factor of 100 and measured in duplicates. The UV-vis spectrometer was tuned in accordance to the manufacturer's specification. In order to increase the limit of detection 5 cm cuvettes were used. Thus, a (LoD) of 20 µg/L was achieved. The extinction coefficient was determined by complete dissolution of the pigments in concentrated H₂SO₄. The peak to valley adsorption was used to calculate the concentration of the dissolved species after dissolution.

The time-resolved concentrations in the sampled eluates c_i and the fluid volume flow V_i of each sampling with duration Δt_i are evaluated towards the dissolved mass $M_{\text{diss}, i}$ by correcting for the stoichiometry:

$$M_{\text{diss}, i} = \frac{m(NF)}{m(\text{ion})} c_i(\text{ion}) V_i \Delta t_i$$

All dissolved mass is summed up to construct the total undissolved mass, and, by assuming a shrinking sphere geometry (Utembe et al., 2015), the surface area SA_i . Instantaneous dissolution rates are constructed for each sampling as: $k_i = M_{\text{diss}, i} / SA_i / \Delta t_i$. The average dissolution rate is obtained by averaging the instantaneous rates. The conversion from rate to a calculated half-time by $T_{1/2} = \frac{\ln 2}{k^*_{\text{BET}}}$ is well-established (Utembe et al., 2015). Additionally, we also fit the dissolution kinetics by an exponential decay to obtain the half-time.

For transmission electron microscopy (TEM) the particles were prepared and centrifuged after dissolution onto a TEM grid as described earlier (Keller et al., 2020c; Koltermann-Jüly et al., 2018), then analyzed with a Tecnai G2-F20ST or Tecnai Osiris Microscope (FEI Company, Hillsboro, USA) at an acceleration voltage of 200 keV under bright field conditions. Images were automatically analyzed through the validated NanoDefine software with validated ParticleSizer module (Verleyen et al., 2019; Wagner, 2016).

3. Results

In order to better understand the complexity of the processes within the pulmonary tract the dissolution of ENM in the two main compartments, in lung lining simulant fluid (LSF) as well as phagolysosomal simulant fluid (PSF) needs to be measured. The PSF mimics the acidic conditions particles are exposed to during phagocytosis, whereas the LSF mimics the lung lining fluid (Fig. 1). To assess the dissolution of nanomaterials, a well-established continuous flow-through system (CFS) as described by ISO 19057 and as previously implemented by Koltermann-

Jüly et al. was used (ISO/TR19057, 2017; Koltermann-Jüly et al., 2019). The flow in this setup mimics the continuous physiological renewal of body fluids, whereby ions can be transported. The operational conditions, especially the volume flow per surface area, were used as optimized previously using benchmark materials (Keller et al., 2020c). The dissolution rates and half-times as well as the transformation of 17 different nanomaterials were measured in both relevant physiological media (Tables 2, 3). The results obtained for PSF pH 4.5 (Table 3) were partly reproduced from Koltermann-Jüly et al. (Koltermann-Jüly et al., 2019) and Keller et al. (2020).

3.1. BaSO₄ NM220

The solubility of BaSO₄ NM220 is especially dependent on the pH of the media and is therefore considered a borderline soluble material. We found no significant dissolution in LSF (Table 2). The dissolution rate between the two tested media differed by a factor of more than 1000. Also the half-time (Tables 2, 3) as calculated exhibited a 1477-fold difference between LSF and PSF. This can be easily explained through the pH dependent dissolution of bulk BaSO₄ (Zhen-Wu et al., 2016). BaSO₄ is highly sensitive to pH changes and does not dissolve in neutral pH,

Table 2
Dissolution rate k and half times of tested NFs in LSF.

Material	Dissolution medium	Half time from mono-exponential fit	Half time calculated from total dissolution (assuming mono-exponential)	Dissolution rate k
		[d]	[d]	[ng/cm ² /h]
Ag NM300K	LSF pH 7.4	72.2	51.6	0.80
BaSO4 NM220	LSF pH 7.4	14,441	9898	0.01
CeO2 NM212	LSF pH 7.4	7220	6209	0.02
CuPhthalo_halogen	LSF pH 7.4	5776	3657	0.01
CuPhthalo_nano	LSF pH 7.4	7220	4211	0.01
DPP_nano	LSF pH 7.4	14,441	7693	0.004
DPP_non-nano	LSF pH 7.4	722	600	0.30
DPP_pre-mixed	LSF pH 7.4	578	393	0.46
Fe2O3_nano_A	LSF pH 7.4	7220	4370	0.01
Fe2O3_nano_B	LSF pH 7.4	5776	3859	0.02
Silica_Al	LSF pH 7.4	3.6	3.9	4.19
Silica_anis_Al	LSF pH 7.4	3.6	3.1	3.76
Silica_anis_Std	LSF pH 7.4	0.2	1.1	12.8
Silica_Silane	LSF pH 7.4	0.5	0.7	19.7
Silica_Std	LSF pH 7.4	0.3	0.5	25.7
SiO2 NM200	LSF pH 7.4	3.6	4.5	3.89
TiO2 NM105	LSF pH 7.4	413	320	0.18
ZnO NM110	LSF pH 7.4	4126	3552	0.07

Table 3
Dissolution rate k and half times of tested NFs in PSF.

Material	Dissolution medium	Half time from mono-exponential fit	Half time calculated from total dissolution (assuming mono-exponential)	Dissolution rate k
		[d]	[d]	[ng/cm ² /h]
Ag NM300K	PSF pH 4.5	289	284	0.15
BaSO ₄ NM220	PSF pH 4.5	7.2	6.7	10.45
CeO ₂ NM212	PSF pH 4.5	2888	2263	0.05
CuPhthalo_halogen	PSF pH 4.5	n/a	>3000	<0.01
CuPhthalo_nano	PSF pH 4.5	n/a	>4000	<0.01
DPP_nano	PSF pH 4.5	144,406	126,177	0.00024
DPP_non-nano	PSF pH 4.5	962,704	873,809	0.00021
DPP_premixed	PSF pH 4.5	289	644	0.28
Fe ₂ O ₃ _nano_A	PSF pH 4.5	963	679	0.04
Fe ₂ O ₃ _nano_B	PSF pH 4.5	3610	2352	0.041
Silica_Al	PSF pH 4.5	4.1	4.1	3.98
Silica_anis_Al	PSF pH 4.5	3.6	4.0	1.70
Silica_anis_Std	PSF pH 4.5	3.6	4.5	3.02
Silica_Silane	PSF pH 4.5	3.2	3.6	3.76
Silica_Std	PSF pH 4.5	2.4	3.9	3.59
SiO ₂ NM200	PSF pH 4.5	29	35	0.39
TiO ₂ NM105	PSF pH 4.5	n/a	>700	0.056
ZnO NM110	PSF pH 4.5	0.7	0.9	231.1

whereas oxidative or reactive processes (Gray et al., 2018) or ion scavengers (Innes et al., 2021) have less influence for this material. The dissolution curve of BaSO₄ NM220 deviated from a mono-exponential decay as evidenced by >2-fold different halftimes obtained by fitting versus calculation (Keller et al., 2020). This indicated a deviation from the shrinking sphere model as a result of local solubility limits as well as particle transformation within PSF. This observation was also confirmed in vivo through high resolution TEM on lung slices (Keller et al., 2020).

3.2. Ag NM300

For Ag NM300, the dissolution rate was faster in LSF compared to PSF by a factor of 5 (Tables 2, 3). This observation is also confirmed in the exponential half-time. The actual dissolution of Ag, however, might be faster than observed since membrane interactions interfere. For both tested media, Ag ions tend to attach to the cellulose triacetate membrane and cannot be quantitatively detected in the eluate by ICP-MS. The loss of Ag from the dissolved state of was experimentally verified by total ashing and acid digestion of the filter, housing and tubings to which the simulant fluid has contact after the flow cell. Ag was found in each of the components. Obviously such a destructive procedure is not sustainable as analytical approach, and hence we could not derive a quantitative Ag dissolution rate.

3.3. Fe₂O₃-NFs and CuPhthalocyanine-NFs

At a very low level of dissolved ions, also Fe₂O₃ NFs showed an accelerated dissolution in PSF over LSF, but half-times were always longer than 963d (Tables 2, 3). Also both CuPhthalocyanine NFs show a faster dissolution in PSF when compared to LSF, but here the initial release of Cu under acidic conditions was attributed to an impurity, not to the particle, because of the non-exponential shape of the kinetics. The descriptors given in Tables 2 and 3 relate to the UVVis-based disintegration of the organic constituents. On the morphological transformation of CuPhthalocyanine_halogen (Fig. S5 C,D) we observed a strong agglomeration or even aggregation (reduction of accessible surface) of the individual particles. Morphological transformation at the very slow dissolution rates $k < 0.1$ might not be relevant from a toxicological point of view.

3.4. SiO₂-NFs

The silicate nanoforms exhibited a significantly faster dissolution in the neutral pH of LSF compared to the more acidic PSF (Tables 2, 3). The shape of the dissolution kinetics is not always monoexponential (Fig. 3). This observation was made for all amorphous silica materials, including SiO₂ NM200, which was the only precipitated silica NF tested. Interestingly, the TEM images (Fig. 2, Fig. S5) showed significant transformation. For some of the amorphous silica materials, the pristine particles were still recognisable, such as Silica_Std and Silica_anis_Std in PSF. For other NFs, including Silica_Al, Silica_anis_Al and Silica_Silane (Fig. 2E), the particles transformed into several large supraparticles, connected silica networks with pores of different sizes. Here it was nearly impossible to detect pristine particles anymore. TEM images of selected samples were analyzed by automated particle detection using the imageJ ParticleSizer plugin (Wagner, 2016). The min feret diameter as well as the shape are usual descriptors for nanoparticles and are listed in Table S6. The result of the automated particle detection for the silica samples is demonstrated on Fig. S7. The particle contour that was fitted by the software is highlighted by a red line. The resulting numerical differences between pristine and transformed materials are summarized by Fig. 4. For Silica_silane, particles were evaluated with significantly smaller diameter than the pristine NF, but these are not representative of structures within the dense aggregates, where no particles were recognised (Fig. S7). Shape and min Feret diameter are common descriptors for nanoparticles (Mech et al., 2020b; Verleysen et al., 2020; Verleysen et al., 2019), but the automated image evaluation of the outer contour of the particles allows the calculation of many additional geometrical descriptors (Wagner, 2016). A complete list is given in Table S8, and numerical results in Fig. 4. The geometrical descriptors can be clustered by their dimension (r^2 , r , dimensionless). Fig. 4 shows how well different geometrical descriptors respond to changes of silica particles during dissolution. The median for each descriptor was calculated and normalized by calculation of Max/Min of each median for the series of pristine, aged LSF and aged PSF. Min. feret was found to be a good choice for the cluster of descriptors with dimension r . Descriptors with dimension r^2 (area) also differentiated between the NFs but did not discriminate better than min Feret diameter. For dimensionless descriptors, “elongation” showed a wider range of values between NFs (Fig. 4) than the more conventional choice “aspect ratio”, but is in fact only a mathematical transformation of the same underlying descriptors S and L (Table S8). Both cannot reproduce the visual impression that silica networks formed for some materials leading to a loss of particle boundaries. The quality of automated recognition of transformation is limited by the first step, the contour recognition of particles. Comparing pristine vs. LSF shapes for SiO₂ NM200 or Silica_anis_Al (Fig. 2), the human eye perceives a change from agglomerates of spherical particles to a porous network consisting of elongated fibrilles and nodes. The ParticleSizer Software is not programmed to recognize such structures, but fits particle contours into the fibrilles (Fig. S7) and thus underestimates the qualitative structural transformation.

The time dependent dissolution kinetics (Fig. 3) supported faster dissolution within neutral pH, explaining the transformation from single particles to porous silica networks which was not observed in PSF. The substantial retardation of dissolution after the first hours matches the observation of the structural transformation with a partial loss of accessible surfaces. Three of the particles, Silica_Std, SiO₂ NM200 and Silica_anis_Std almost completely dissolved after 7d. Besides the modulation by the simulant fluid, another modulation by the NF differences was seen. The Al-doped NFs dissolved slower than the SiO₂ NF without Al doping. The shape did not matter that much for dissolution behavior, nor the organic surface treatment by silanes. The observed transformation behavior of the silica NFs is in agreement with recent in vivo transformations as observed by Graham et al. (2017). There, a significant in vivo solubility was detected with simultaneous transformation of phagocytosed SiO₂ at 27 days post treatment. SiO₂ lost its spherical

Fig. 2. TEM results of particle transformation before the dissolution (left), after 7d in pH 7.4 LSF (middle) and independently after 7d in pH 4.5 PSF (right). A: Silica Std, B: Silica anis Std, C: Silica Al, D: Silica anis Al, E: Silica Silane and F: SiO₂ NM200. See Table S5 for the numerical assessment of transformation by automated TEM image analysis before and after dissolution testing.

Fig. 3. Time dependent dissolution kinetics of silica materials. Orange corresponds to LSF, whereas blue corresponds to PSF. Δ Silica_Std, \ast Silica_AI, \square Silica_Anis_AI, \diamond Silica_anis_Std, \times SiO₂ NM200, \bullet Silica Silane. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

structure almost completely and formed a porous network (Graham et al., 2017). The same observation was made here in the abiotic CFS system. After 7 days dissolution in LSF all silica NFs lost their pristine nanoform and some clearly formed a nanoporous structure (Fig. 2). Therefore, colloidal silica is considered as partially dissolving.

3.5. Transformation of NFs other than silica

Transformation with aggregation and partial loss of the original particle shape, as observed for the silica materials in LSF, was not detected for any other materials studied here, except that BaSO₄ showed Ostwald ripening and CuPhthalocyanine showed strong agglomeration or aggregation (partial loss of accessible surface). There were also some

particles with no transformation or aggregation at all. Our benchmark materials for this behavior are CeO₂ NM212 and Fe₂O₃_nano_B (Fig. S5, Table S6). Here we did not observe aggregation (Fig. S5), and also with the automated TEM evaluation (Table S6) no changes were observed. There are several other materials where no transformation occurred, such as Fe₂O₃_nano_A, as well as all three tested DPP NFs. Furthermore, ZnO NM110 did not dissolve, and did not transform in pH 7.4 LSF fluid. In summary, no significant transformation was noted for materials with $k < 0.1$ ng/cm²/h. However, for moderately dissolving materials such as BaSO₄ NM220 and the silicates, substantial transformation can be observed up to $k = 10$ ng/cm²/h, with matching abiotic and in vivo observations.

Fig. 4. Methodical comparison of different geometrical descriptors by ParticleSizer. Plotted is the spread of the medians of each descriptor for pristine, aged_LSF and aged_PSF, on the example of four silica NFs. Descriptors that are insensitive to transformation will have a spread closer to 1 than the more sensitive descriptors. The descriptors are defined in Table S8. Results from Silica_silane as aged in LSF were not included because the detection by TEM is not representative of the structures within dense aggregates (See Fig. S7) as discussed in the text.

4. Discussion

The outcome of the GRACIOUS framework is aimed to help the user to decide if endpoint-specific grouping and read-across is justified for a candidate group of NFs, or a selection thereof (Stone et al., 2020). Such selection is needed if some candidate group members are not sufficiently similar to the others. Establishing groups based on pre-fixed boundaries (e.g., dissolution half-time up to 1 day, between 1 and 5 days, or between 5 and 60 days) would necessarily lead to non logical conclusions in which NFs that are objectively similar (e.g. a few hours difference, but on either side of the pre-fixed boundary) would not allow read-across. Instead, we propose to justify groups based on sufficient similarity of every pair of NFs within that group. When each pair of NFs in a group is similar, also the entire group is similar (Janer et al., 2021). For larger groups this requires many pairwise assessments. An example is given in Tables 4 and 5, where we use the simple algorithm of x-fold difference as numerical measure of dissimilarity. It was earlier used by the Guidenano framework (Park et al., 2018) and by the assessment of sets of similar NFs by the ECETOC NanoApp (Janer et al., 2021). The x-fold algorithm is well adapted to the dissolution property, which spans at least four orders of magnitude (Table 2) and thus requires a logarithmic axis (that is, x-fold axis ticks, similar to the log k_{ow} descriptor of non-nano chemicals). Two different descriptors can be used for the NF comparison: the dissolution rate, which is a surface-based metric, is more appropriate to identify differences in the mechanism of dissolution (Table 4), whereas the half-time, being a mass-based metric, is more appropriate for hazard assessment (Table 5). The conversion from rate to half-time by $T_{1/2} = \frac{\ln 2}{k \cdot BET}$ is well-established (Utembe et al., 2015) and implies that differences in specific surface area can compensate or exacerbate differences of the dissolution rate: at the same dissolution rate, a smaller NF has shorter half-time than a larger NF.

Partially dissolving materials are most sensitive as test cases of the methodology. Comparing SiO₂ NM200 to Silica_std, the similarity in dissolution rate was already limited at 6.61-fold and 6.19-fold for LSF pH 7.4 and PSF pH 4.5, respectively (Table 4), but was even less similar at 8.29-fold and 9.03-fold for the corresponding half-times (Table 5). In the PSF pH 4.5 fluid, all colloidal silica materials tested here differed less than 1.26-fold in any pairwise comparison of half-times. In the LSF pH 7.4 fluid, a different pattern emerged (Table 5): the half-times of the spheroidal Al-doped and elongated Al-doped NFs were 1.26-fold

different; the half-times of Silica_std, Silica_anis_std and Silica_silane were up to 1.55-fold different. However, between the NFs that were Al-doped and those that were not, the similarity was low with up to 7.28-fold difference. The least similarity with nearly 10-fold difference was observed between NM200 and Silica_silane in PSF.

The color code in Tables 4 and 5 highlights identical values (x-fold similarity = 1) in green, and highlights x-fold similarity ≥ 5 in red. The ECETOC NanoApp accepts up to 5-fold difference in dissolution half-time as criterion of sufficiently similarity (Janer et al., 2021), and it can be justified as follows: If the remaining solids (NF that have not dissolved) raise more concern than the dissolved ions, the example of mineral fibers has ample in-vivo data and dissolution data. The WHO reported that within the range of dissolution rates k from 13 to 329 ng/cm²/h (25-fold difference) the observed effects varied from fibrosis and tumors to no effects, and at $k = 72$ ng/cm²/h (5-fold to either side) only fibrosis was observed (IARC, 2002). Dissolution was believed to be the determinant descriptor in this case (IARC, 2002; Oberdörster, 2000). If the released metal ions would induce adverse effects, then potential differences in toxicity due to different dissolution half-times of up to 5-fold would be within the usual width of the STOT RE categories used for CLP classification (10-fold), and are below the reported inter-study variability for repeated dose toxicity studies (around 5 to 10-fold for oral studies) derived from relatively large datasets on classical substances (Friedman, 2019). Although the datasets are much more limited for nanomaterials, they suggest that NF inter-study variability may even exceed inter-study variability for non-nano-chemicals (Drew et al., 2017; Scoville et al., 2015). From a toxicological and regulatory perspective, the factor 5 thus seems adequate. The metrological perspective does not contradict this: Similarity factors lower than the reproducibility of the assay cannot be interpreted. Reproducibility of the CFS method was 60% (a factor 1.6) with a tightly controlled SOP and for a narrow class of test item composition (Guldberg et al., 2003), whereas for NFs we observe a factor 2 intralab variation (data not shown) and more between labs. Factors between 2 and 5 are thus metrologically relevant and toxicologically acceptable.

In the GRACIOUS integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATA) for inhalation hazard, similar dissolution rates alone do not justify grouping. As suggested by other grouping frameworks and ECHA guidance, the IATA in the GRACIOUS framework will require data on additional properties, such as in vitro toxicity or surface reactivity. The joint assessment will enable the identification of a worst case NF that

Table 4
Pairwise similarity of dissolution rate k between each tested Silica material.

dissolution rate k	Silica_std	Silica_anis_std	Silica_Al	Silica_anis_Al	Silica_silane	SiO ₂ NM200
LSF pH 7.4						
Silica_std		2.01	6.14	6.84	1.30	6.61
Silica_anis_std	1.19		3.06	3.41	1.54	3.29
Silica_Al	1.11	1.32		1.11	4.71	1.08
Silica_anis_Al	2.11	1.78	2.34		5.24	1.03
Silica_silane	1.05	1.25	1.06	2.21		5.07
SiO ₂ NM200	6.19	5.20	6.86	2.93	6.49	
PSF pH 4.5						

Above the diagonal, the dissolution in LSF is compared between the various NFs. Below the diagonal, the same for PSF. The values are x-fold differences and are calculated by dividing the larger value by the smaller value. Green indicates values close to 1 (strong similarity or even identical values in the functional assays despite different physical-chemical parameters). Red indicates values of more than 5-fold dissimilarity.

Table 5
Pairwise similarity of half-time between each tested Silica material.

half time	Silica_std	Silica_anis_std	Silica_Al	Silica_anis_Al	Silica_silane	SiO ₂ NM200
LSF pH 7.4						
Silica_std		1.96	7.28	5.78	1.26	8.29
Silica_anis_std	1.16		3.72	2.95	1.55	4.24
Silica_Al	1.07	1.08		1.26	5.78	1.14
Silica_anis_Al	1.03	1.13	1.04		4.59	1.44
Silica_silane	1.08	1.26	1.16	1.12		8.29
SiO ₂ NM200	9.03	7.76	8.41	8.74	9.77	
PSF pH 4.5						

Above the diagonal, the dissolution in LSF is compared between the various NFs. Below the diagonal, the same for PSF. The values are x-fold differences and are calculated by dividing the larger value by the smaller value. Green indicates values close to 1 (strong similarity or even identical values in the functional assay despite different physical-chemical parameters). Red indicates values of more than 5-fold dissimilarity.

should be used as representative NF of the entire group (or not included in this group and separately be evaluated) to gather the in vivo inhalation toxicity data using current OECD testing guidelines 412 and/or 413 as required by REACH, which can then be used for read across to the other similar NFs in the group. Whether the 5-fold factor in similarity is an acceptable limit can be judged only with additional data on properties other than dissolution. Then, one might assess each property independently of the others or jointly, and one will require in vivo inhalation toxicity data on some NFs of the same substance to “calibrate” the assessment. This is beyond the scope of the present contribution, which lays the basis for such an analysis. Case studies are reported by Janer et al. and by Ma-Hock et al. in this special issue.

For the specific example of colloidal silica, the dissolution does not exclude grouping of Silica_std, Silica_anis_std and Silica_silane. It does also not exclude grouping of Silica_al and Silica_anis_Al. However, the more than 5-fold differences *between* these two groups suggest that these two candidate groups cannot be merged into one larger group. Table 5 also suggests that all of the colloidal silica NFs tested here cannot be grouped with SiO₂ NM200, which is a precipitated silica which behaved differently with regard to dissolution.

Apart from amorphous silica, many of the NFs tested here had very slow dissolution half-times. In such cases, differences in dissolution half-times may become less relevant than all other properties. What would then be the biologically relevant range of pulmonary dissolution half-times? Physiological time-scales range from a few hours of macrophage invasion (Bowden, 1984) to around 60 days of physiological clearance from alveoli (Oberdörster and Kuhlbusch, 2018). With regard to particle-triggered toxicity, a dissolution half-time of 1 h or 1 min does not make a biological difference; both imply that biodegradability is not a concern, and that effects will be dominated by ions, not by NF particles. Likewise, a dissolution half-time of 1 year or 10 years does not make a biological difference; both indicate biodegradability, and imply that accumulation might be a concern, and the effects are dominated by the NFs, not by ions. If the dissolution half-time would be one year and the physiological clearance half-time by macrophages is 60 days, the effective half-time (biological plus physical) would be 52 days. This difference is within the variation of the physiological clearance half-times. Thus, dissolution half-times longer than 1 year do not change our assessment of accumulation and biokinetics. If the ions would be significantly more hazardous than the particles, then dissolution half-times between 60 days and one year are a borderline range where

dissolution still contributes to clearance (Oberdörster and Kuhlbusch, 2018), and where the release of ions may need to be considered additionally to the NF toxicity, as demonstrated for surface-induced reactivity (Peijnenburg et al., 2020). Based on these considerations, an assessment of similarity can be omitted for NF with dissolution half-time below 1 h or above 1 year, and the range between 1 h and 1 year (=8760 h) describes the biologically relevant range.

- Below that range, similarity of dissolution does not need to be considered, because clearance is anyway dominated by dissolution, and effects dominated by ions. ZnO is the best available benchmark material for such behavior, even though ZnO is borderline at 0.7 to 0.9 days half-time, and only under lysosomal conditions (Table 3), and was often discussed in literature regarding the contribution of ions and particles to toxicity (Anders et al., 2018; Hadrup et al., 2019; Ivask et al., 2017). MoO₃ nanoribbons might be an example for instantaneous (few minutes) dissolution in lining fluid (Gray et al., 2018).
- Above that range, similarity of dissolution does not need to be considered, because the contribution to clearance is within the variation of the physiological clearance half-times. This would be fulfilled for the tested DPP NFs, Fe₂O₃, CuPhthalocyanine, TiO₂, and CeO₂. They all have very slow half-times above 1 year in both fluids. The seven different pigments including three DPP NFs, two CuPhthalocyanine NFs and two Fe₂O₃ NFs belong to the category of very slow dissolving NFs with a half-time >60d, and even >1y. The organic DPP materials dissolved more rapidly in LSF than in PSF by a factor 4 to 11. On DPP and Fe₂O₃ pigments, no transformation was observed in either medium, but for both CuPhthalocyanine a strong agglomeration or even aggregation (partial loss of accessible surface) was detected in PSF (Fig. S5).
- Within the biologically relevant range, an assessment of partial dissolution with pairwise comparison of the similarity between NFs would be required for NFs of Ag, SiO₂, BaSO₄. Uptake and in vivo processing by alveolar macrophages is the primary mechanism of clearance, or a dissolution within the lysosome with transformation or complete dissolution may occur. Table 5 and the above discussion provide an example of such assessment on six silica NFs.

Additionally, our TEM analysis has assessed biotransformation of dissolved ions in the biological media, which may occur by precipitation

with inorganic or organic components of the medium. One can conclude that the assessment of *physical* transformation by TEM under pulmonary conditions is grossly consistent with the assessment of similarity of dissolution rates or half-times, but much harder to assess experimentally and harder to quantify numerically; it did not change our interpretation of pairwise similarity between silica NFs. The changes in size (Table S5) are moderate, and might not be representative, because only particles large enough to be centrifuged onto the TEM grid can be observed (introducing bias), and because diameter scales with cube root of particle mass (being far less sensitive than the direct observation of ions). None of the 16 ParticleSizer descriptors is recommended as additional similarity criterion for an inhalation IATA of a grouping framework (Stone et al., 2020), whereas *chemical* transformation, e.g. cleavage of surface treatments or sulfidation of metals under environmental conditions (and longer time scales) can be a powerful grouping approach for different endpoints (Conway et al., 2015; Lynch et al., 2014; Mitrano et al., 2015; Pantano et al., 2018).

Of note, the assessment of pairwise similarity would have been completely different, had we only tested PSF pH 4.5 conditions: one would have placed both Al_doped and standard colloidal silica into one large candidate group, separating only NM200 (Table 5, below the diagonal). Differences observed in LSF pH 7.4 are considered relevant since dissolution of silica-based materials, such as glass fibers, is known to occur preferentially at neutral pH (Paul, 1989). However, silica is special in this regard (Iler, 1979), as there are more materials (most metals, here also ZnO, BaSO₄, Carbonates etc) that dissolve faster in acidic pH and under oxidative conditions (Gray et al., 2018). We suggest that testing the dissolution in lysosomal pH 4.5 conditions should remain the main screening tool in a first tier, and only for materials with known susceptibility to dissolution in neutral pH, also lung lining pH 7.4 conditions should be added.

5. Conclusions

Within this study, the dissolution and structural transformation of 17 NFs of varying chemical composition, size, shape, surface area and surface functionalization were investigated within the continuous flow system (CFS, ISO19057) in two different compartments, lung lining simulant (pH 7.4 LSF) and lysosomal simulant (pH 4.5 PSF). We developed and performed a pairwise comparison between NFs that helped to identify different dissolution mechanisms via surface-based rates and different clearance times via mass-based half-times. We found that the dissolution half-times spanned nearly five orders of magnitude, mostly dictated by the substance and simulant fluid, but modulated up to ten-fold by the subtle differences between NFs of silica. We suggest that testing dissolution in lysosomal pH 4.5 conditions should remain the main screening tool in a first tier, and only for materials with known susceptibility to neutral pH, also lung lining pH 7.4 conditions should be added. Structural transformations were observed especially in cases of dissolution rates on the order of 0.1 to 10 ng/cm²/h, confirming earlier correlations between in vivo and abiotic observations (Keller et al., 2020). This confirms the expectation that some dissolution is required to mediate biotransformation via reprecipitation of dissolved ions into thermodynamically favorable structures within the biological media. However, the assessment of transformation did not provide additional insight on the similarity between NFs, potentially due to methodical limitations, and is -at present- not proposed as criterion for grouping and read-across for the endpoint of lung toxicity.

Evidence on dissolution alone cannot justify grouping, but the current contribution enables a discussion of acceptable similarity in comprehensive case studies, such as those by Jeliakova et al. and by Ma-Hock et al. (in the same special issue), which consider additionally the similarity of in vitro toxicity or surface reactivity, and compare the overall similarity by screening methods to the similarity of toxicity in inhalation studies. Considering STOT RE categories used for CLP classification and the inter-study variability for repeated dose toxicity

studies, we explored the working hypothesis that up to 5-fold similarity in dissolution half-time could be acceptable to form a group, of which the worst case NF is further assessed for the REACH data requirements by in vivo inhalation studies. In the case of silica, the ions have low toxicity, and the worst case NF for each group would be the NF with slowest dissolution, because it will persist as particle for longer, and may induce effects as particle. The 5-fold rule divided the colloidal silica NFs into two separate candidate groups, one with Al-doping, one without. Indeed, based on the results of a recently performed 90-day inhalation toxicity study with amorphous silicas (unpublished results), it is clear that although the Al-doped silica (silica_Al) in general showed qualitatively the same histopathological changes in lung and lymph nodes at the same exposure concentration as the non Al-doped ones (silica_Silane and silica_Std), the histopathological changes induced by the Al-doped form were quantitatively more severe; the order of toxicity from high to low was: silica_Al, silica_Std, and then silica_Silane. In addition, after the 90-day recovery period, less recovery was observed with silica_Al compared to the silane-treated silica. Once published, the in vivo results allow to calibrate the acceptable similarity of dissolution (and other properties), but the currently available knowledge is fully consistent with the proposals made here.

Funding

This work was part of the GRACIOUS project supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the grant agreement No 760840.

Declaration of competing interest

JGK, LMH, PM, KW, RL, WW are working for BASF SE, a company producing nanomaterials. MP and JA work for Nouryon, a company producing colloidal silicas.

Acknowledgement

We thank Thorsten Wieczorek for excellent laboratory support on TEM imaging. We thank Nathan Bossa (LEITAT, Barcelona), Nicklas Monster Salgren (NRCWE, Copenhagen), Björn Stolpe (Nouryon, Bohus), Hubert Rauscher (JRC, Ispra), Richard Cross (CEH, Wallingford), Frederic Loosli (University of Vienna) for the contributions to the basic characterisation of GRACIOUS materials, and Daniel Persson (Nouryon, Bohus), for discussion.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.impact.2021.100341>.

References

- Anders, C.B., Eixenberger, J.E., Franco, N.A., Hermann, R.J., Rainey, K.D., Chess, J.J., Punnoose, A., Wingett, D.G., 2018. ZnO nanoparticle preparation route influences surface reactivity, dissolution and cytotoxicity. *Environ. Sci.* 5 (2), 572–588.
- Arts, J.H., Hadi, M., Keene, A.M., Kreiling, R., Lyon, D., Maier, M., Michel, K., Petry, T., Sauer, U.G., Warheit, D., 2014. A critical appraisal of existing concepts for the grouping of nanomaterials. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 70 (2), 492–506.
- Arts, J.H., Hadi, M., Irfan, M.-A., Keene, A.M., Kreiling, R., Lyon, D., Maier, M., Michel, K., Petry, T., Sauer, U.G., 2015. A decision-making framework for the grouping and testing of nanomaterials (DF4nanoGrouping). *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 71 (2), S1–S27.
- Arts, J.H., Irfan, M.-A., Keene, A.M., Kreiling, R., Lyon, D., Maier, M., Michel, K., Neubauer, N., Petry, T., Sauer, U.G., 2016. Case studies putting the decision-making framework for the grouping and testing of nanomaterials (DF4nanoGrouping) into practice. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 76, 234–261.
- Avramescu, M.-L., Chénier, M., Palaniyandi, S., Rasmussen, P.E., 2020. Dissolution behavior of metal oxide nanomaterials in cell culture medium versus distilled water. *J. Nanopart. Res.* 22 (8), 222.
- Bowden, D.H., 1984. The alveolar macrophage. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 55, 327–341.

- Cai, X., Liu, X., Jiang, J., Gao, M., Wang, W., Zheng, H., Xu, S., Li, R., 2020. Molecular mechanisms, characterization methods, and utilities of nanoparticle biotransformation in nanosafety assessments. *Small* 19(7)663.
- Commission, E., 2018. Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/1881 of 3 December 2018 amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) as regards Annexes I, III, VI, VII, VIII, IX, X, XI, and XII to address nanoforms of substances (Text with EEA relevance.). C/2018/7942. E. Commission.
- Conway, J.R., Adeleye, A.S., Gardea-Torresdey, J., Keller, A.A., 2015. Aggregation, dissolution, and transformation of copper nanoparticles in natural waters. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 49 (5), 2749–2756.
- De Meringo, A., Morscheidt, C., Thélohan, S., Tiesler, H., 1994. In vitro assessment of biodegradability: acellular systems. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 102 (Suppl. 5), 47.
- Drew, N.M., Kuempel, E.D., Pei, Y., Yang, F., 2017. A quantitative framework to group nanoscale and microscale particles by hazard potency to derive occupational exposure limits: Proof of concept evaluation. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 89 (Supplement C), 253–267.
- European Chemical Agency (ECHA), 2019. Appendix R.6–1 for Nanoforms Applicable to the Guidance on QSARs and Grouping of Chemicals. ECHA-19-H-15-EN. ECHA.
- European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), 2019. Appendix for Nanoforms Applicable to the Guidance on Registration and Substance Identification. ECHA-19-H-14-EN. ECHA.
- Friedman, K., 2019. https://www.epa.gov/sites/production/files/2020-01/documents/4_508_katie_paulfriedman_nams_2019.pdf.
- Fuentes, C., Ruiz-Rico, M., Fuentes, A., Ruiz, M.J., Barat, J.M., 2020. Degradation of silica particles functionalised with essential oil components under simulated physiological conditions. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 399, 123120.
- Gao, X., Lowry, G.V., 2018. Progress towards standardized and validated characterizations for measuring physicochemical properties of manufactured nanomaterials relevant to nano health and safety risks. *NanoImpact* 9 (Supplement C), 14–30.
- Graham, U.M., Jacobs, G., Yokel, R.A., Davis, B.H., Dozier, A.K., Birch, M.E., Tseng, M.T., Oberdörster, G., Elder, A., DeLouise, L., 2017. In: Tran, L., Bañares, M.A., Rallo, R. (Eds.), *From Dose to Response: In Vivo Nanoparticle Processing and Potential Toxicity. Modelling the Toxicity of Nanoparticles*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 71–100.
- Gray, E.P., Browning, C.L., Wang, M., Gion, K.D., Chao, E.Y., Koski, K.J., Kane, A.B., Hurt, R.H., 2018. Biodissolution and cellular response to MoO₃ nanoribbons and a new framework for early hazard screening for 2D materials. *Environ. Sci.* 5 (11), 2545–2559.
- Gray, E.P., Browning, C.L., Vaslet, C.A., Gion, K.D., Green, A., Liu, M., Kane, A.B., Hurt, R.H., 2020. Chemical and colloidal dynamics of MnO₂ nanosheets in biological media relevant for nanosafety assessment. *Small* 16 (21), 2000303.
- Gualtieri, A.F., Lusvardi, G., Zoboli, A., Di Giuseppe, D., Lassinantti Gualtieri, M., 2019. Biodurability and release of metals during the dissolution of chrysotile, crocidolite and fibrous erionite. *Environ. Res.* 171, 550–557.
- Guldberg, M., Christensen, V.R., Krois, W., Sebastian, K., 1995. Method for determining in-vitro dissolution rates of man-made vitreous fibres. *Glas. Sci. Technol.* 68 (6), 181–187.
- Guldberg, M., Christensen, V.R., Perander, M., Zoitos, B., Koenig, A.R., Sebastian, K., 1998. Measurement of in-vitro fibre dissolution rate at acidic pH. *Ann. Occup. Hyg.* 42 (4), 233–243.
- Guldberg, M., Madsen, A.L., Sebastian, K., Fellman, J., Potter, R., Corning, O., Bauer, J., Manville, J., Searl, A., Maquin, B., 2003. In-vitro dissolution of vitreous silicate fibres according to EURIMA test guideline: results of two round robins. *Glas. Sci. Technol.* 76 (4), 199–205.
- Hadrup, N., Rahmani, F., Jacobsen, N.R., Saber, A.T., Jackson, P., Bengtson, S., Williams, A., Wallin, H., Halappanavar, S., Vogel, U., 2019. Acute phase response and inflammation following pulmonary exposure to low doses of zinc oxide nanoparticles in mice. *Nanotoxicology* 1–18.
- Hattendorf, B., Günther, D., 2004. Suppression of in-cell generated interferences in a reaction cell ICP-MS by bandpass tuning and kinetic energy discrimination. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* 19 (5), 600–606.
- Herbst, W., Hunger, K., 2006. *Industrial Organic Pigments: Production, Properties, Applications*, 3rd, Completely Revised Edition. Wiley.
- IARC, 2002. *Man-Made Vitreous Fibres*. World Health Organization, pp. 1–433.
- Iler, R.K., 1979. *The Chemistry of Silica Solubility, Polymerization, Colloid and Surface Properties, and Biochemistry of Silica*. Wiley.
- Innes, E., Yiu, H.H., McLean, P., Brown, W., Boyles, M., 2021. Simulated biological fluids—a systematic review of their biological relevance and use in relation to inhalation toxicology of particles and fibres. *Crit. Rev. Toxicol.* 51, 217–248.
- ISO/TR19057, 2017. *Nanotechnologies — Use and Application of Acellular In Vitro Tests and Methodologies to Assess Nanomaterial Biodurability*, 19057. ISO/TR.
- Ivask, A., Scheckel, K.G., Kapruwan, P., Stone, V., Yin, H., Voelcker, N.H., Lombi, E., 2017. Complete transformation of ZnO and CuO nanoparticles in culture medium and lymphocyte cells during toxicity testing. *Nanotoxicology* 1–16.
- Janer, G., Landsiedel, R., Wohlleben, W., 2021. Rationale and decision rules behind the ECETOC NanoApp to support registration of sets of similar nanoforms within REACH. *Nanotoxicology* 15, 145–166.
- Kastury, F., Smith, E., Juhasz, A.L., 2017. A critical review of approaches and limitations of inhalation bioavailability and bioaccessibility of metal(loid)s from ambient particulate matter or dust. *Soc. Total Environ.* 574, 1054–1074.
- Keller, J.G., Graham, U.M., Koltermann-Jüly, J., Gelein, R., Ma-Hock, L., Landsiedel, R., Wiemann, M., Oberdörster, G., Elder, A., Wohlleben, W., 2020. Predicting dissolution and transformation of inhaled nanoparticles in the lung using abiotic flow cells: the case of barium sulfate. *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1), 458.
- Keller, J.G., Peijnenburg, W., Werle, K., Landsiedel, R., Wohlleben, W., 2020c. Understanding dissolution rates via continuous flow systems with physiologically relevant metal ion saturation in lysosome. *Nanomaterials* 10 (2), 311.
- Klaessig, F., 2018. Dissolution as a Paradigm in regulating nanomaterials. *Env. Sci. Nano* 5, 1070–1077.
- Koltermann-Jüly, J., Keller, J.G., Vennemann, A., Werle, K., Müller, P., Ma-Hock, L., Landsiedel, R., Wiemann, M., Wohlleben, W., 2018. Abiotic dissolution rates of 24 (nano)forms of 6 substances compared to macrophage-assisted dissolution and in vivo pulmonary clearance: Grouping by biodissolution and transformation. *NanoImpact*.
- Koltermann-Jüly, J., Keller, J.G., Vennemann, A., Werle, K., Müller, P., Ma-Hock, L., Landsiedel, R., Wiemann, M., Wohlleben, W., 2018. Addendum to “Abiotic dissolution rates of 24 (nano) forms of 6 substances compared to macrophage-assisted dissolution and in vivo pulmonary clearance: grouping by biodissolution and transformation” [Nanotoxicology 12 (2018) 29–41]. *NanoImpact* 12, 29–41.
- Lamon, L., Asturiol, D., Richarz, A., Joossens, E., Graepel, R., Aschberger, K., Worth, A., 2018. Grouping of nanomaterials to read-across hazard endpoints: from data collection to assessment of the grouping hypothesis by application of chemoinformatic techniques. *Part. Fibre Toxicol.* 15 (1), 37.
- Lynch, I., Weiss, C., Valsami-Jones, E., 2014. A strategy for grouping of nanomaterials based on key physico-chemical descriptors as a basis for safer-by-design NMs. *Nano Today* 9 (3), 266–270.
- Marques, M., Loebenberg, R., Almukainzi, M., 2011. *Simulated Biological Fluids with Possible Application in Dissolution Testing*. Dissolution Technologies, 8, pp. 15–29.
- Mech, A., Rauscher, H., Rasmussen, K., Babick, F., Hodoroaba, V.-D., Ghanem, A., Wohlleben, W., Marvin, H., Brüngel, R., Friedrich, C.M., 2020a. *The NanoDefine Methods Manual*.
- Mech, A., Wohlleben, W., Ghanem, A., Hodoroaba, V.-D., Weigel, S., Babick, F., Brüngel, R., Friedrich, C.M., Rasmussen, K., Rauscher, H., 2020b. Nano or not nano? A structured approach for identifying nanomaterials according to the European commission’s definition. *Small* 16 (36), 2002228.
- Ministère de l’Environnement, de l’Énergie et de la Mer, 2015. *Éléments Issus des Déclarations des Substances à l’État Nanoparticulaire: Exercice 2015*. Ministère.
- Mitrano, D.M., Motellier, S., Clavaguera, S., Nowack, B., 2015. Review of nanomaterial aging and transformations through the life cycle of nano-enhanced products. *Environ. Int.* 77 (0), 132–147.
- Norell, M., Johansson, K., Persson, M., 1999. Retention and drainage. In: *Papermaking Science and Technology, Book 4: Papermaking Chemistry*, pp. 43–81.
- Oberdörster, G., 2000. Determinants of the pathogenicity of man-made vitreous fibers (MMVF). *Int. Arch. Occup. Environ. Health* 73 (1), S60–S68.
- Oberdörster, G., Kuhlbusch, T.A.J., 2018. In vivo effects: Methodologies and biokinetics of inhaled nanomaterials. *NanoImpact* 10 (Supplement C), 38–60.
- OECD, 2020. GD318: guidance document for the testing of dissolution and dispersion stability of nanomaterials and the use of the data for further environmental testing and assessment strategies. In: *ENV/JM/MONO(2020)9*.
- Oomen, A., Bleeker, E., Bos, P., van Broekhuizen, F., Gottardo, S., Groenewold, M., Hristozov, D., Hund-Rinke, K., Irfan, M.-A., Marcomini, A., 2015. Grouping and read-across approaches for risk assessment of nanomaterials. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 12 (10), 13415–13434.
- Pantano, D., Neubauer, N., Navratilova, J., Scifo, L., Civardi, C., Stone, V., von der Kammer, F., Müller, P., Sobrido, M.S., Angeletti, B., Rose, J., Wohlleben, W., 2018. Transformations of nanoenabled copper formulations govern release, antifungal effectiveness, and sustainability throughout the wood protection lifecycle. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 52, 1128–1138.
- Park, M.V., Catalán, J., Ferraz, N., Cabellos, J., Vanhauven, R., Vázquez-Campos, S., Janer, G., 2018. Development of a systematic method to assess similarity between nanomaterials for human hazard evaluation purposes—lessons learnt. *Nanotoxicology* 12 (7), 652–676.
- Paul, A., 1989. *Chemistry of Glasses*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Peijnenburg, W.J., Ruggiero, E., Boyles, M., Murphy, F., Stone, V., Elam, D.A., Werle, K., Wohlleben, W., 2020. A method to assess the relevance of nanomaterial dissolution during reactivity testing. *Materials* 13 (10), 2235.
- Pfaff, G., 2017. *Inorganic Pigments*. De Gruyter. ISBN 978-3-11-048450-2.
- Scoville, D.K., White, C.C., Botta, D., McConnachie, L.A., Zadworny, M.E., Schmuck, S.C., Hu, X., Gao, X., Yu, J., Dills, R.L., 2015. Susceptibility to quantum dot induced lung inflammation differs widely among the collaborative cross founder mouse strains. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 289 (2), 240–250.
- Stefaniak, A.B., Guilmette, R.A., Day, G.A., Hoover, M.D., Breyse, P.N., Scricsick, R.C., 2005. Characterization of phagolysosomal simulant fluid for study of beryllium aerosol particle dissolution. *Toxicol. in Vitro* 19 (1), 123–134.
- Steinhäuser, K.G., Sayre, P.G., 2017. Reliability of methods and data for regulatory assessment of nanomaterial risks. *NanoImpact* 7 (Supplement C), 66–74.
- Stone, V., Gottardo, S., Bleeker, E.A.J., Braakhuis, H., Dekkers, S., Fernandes, T., Haase, A., Hunt, N., Hristozov, D., Jantunen, P., Jeliazkova, N., Johnston, H., Lamon, L., Murphy, F., Rasmussen, K., Rauscher, H., Jiménez, A.S., Svendsen, C., Spurgeon, D., Vázquez-Campos, S., Wohlleben, W., Oomen, A.G., 2020. A framework for grouping and read-across of nanomaterials—supporting innovation and risk assessment. *Nano Today* 35, 100941.
- Utembe, W., Potgieter, K., Stefaniak, A.B., Gulumian, M., 2015. Dissolution and biodegradability: important parameters needed for risk assessment of nanomaterials. *Part. Fibre Toxicol.* 12 (1), 11.
- Verleysen, E., Wagner, T., Lipinski, H.-G., Kägi, R., Koeber, R., Boix-Sanfelici, A., De Temmerman, P.-J., Mast, J., 2019. Evaluation of a TEM based approach for size measurement of particulate (Nano) materials. *Materials* 12 (14), 2274.

- Verleysen, E., Waegeneers, N., Brassinne, F., De Vos, S., Jimenez, I.O., Mathioudaki, S., Mast, J., 2020. Physicochemical characterization of the pristine E171 food additive by standardized and validated methods. *Nanomaterials* 10 (3), 592.
- Wagner, T., 2016. ij-particlesizer: ParticleSizer 1.0.1. Zenodo.
- Wigger, H., Wohleben, W., Nowack, B., 2018. Redefining environmental nanomaterial flows: consequences of the regulatory nanomaterial definition on the results of environmental exposure models. *Environ. Sci.* 5 (6), 1372–1385.
- Yamada, N., 2015. Kinetic energy discrimination in collision/reaction cell ICP-MS: theoretical review of principles and limitations. *Spectrochim. Acta B At. Spectrosc.* 110, 31–44.
- Yokel, R.A., Hancock, M.L., Grulke, E.A., Unrine, J.M., Dozier, A.K., Graham, U.M., 2019. Carboxylic acids accelerate acidic environment-mediated nanoceria dissolution. *Nanotoxicology* 16, 1–21.
- Zhen-Wu, B., Dideriksen, K., Olsson, J., Raahauge, P., Stipp, S.L.S., Oelkers, E., 2016. Experimental determination of barite dissolution and precipitation rates as a function of temperature and aqueous fluid composition. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 194, 193–210.